

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D6.1

DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN, INCLUDING COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Summary:

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan outlines the key objectives of outreach activities in CRM-geothermal and details the steps to be taken to maximise impact. The plan serves as a basis to define the main groups of stakeholders and their respective needs in a stakeholder matrix. It also provides guidelines for an efficient internal and external project communication. Following its initial submission in October 2022, this document has been updated in April 2024.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan (DEC) for CRM-geothermal and provides internal and external communication guidelines.

This document aims to define communication and dissemination objectives, target audiences, core messages, and key performance indicators to ensure consistency of the outreach activities and maximise impact during and after the project's funding period.

The external communication plan (communication and dissemination) is using a synergetic combination of several channels and tools: a project web site linked with existing high traffic social media channels; regular press releases, webinars and other external event opportunities; online social networking and publications in a range of media outlets and papers including peer-reviewed and non-specialist publications. The overview of the planned communication and dissemination activities provides a concise description of actions designed to mobilise key stakeholders, informing them about the project objectives and expected results.

The plan also serves as a basis for defining the main groups of stakeholders and their respective needs in a stakeholder matrix.

The exploitation plan details the measures taken to facilitate the uptake of the project's results after the end of the funding period.

The internal communication plan defines responsibilities among project partners and describes communication channels and monitoring instruments.

According to the Description of the Action (DoA) of CRM-geothermal, the content and the corresponding implementation will be monitored, updated and adapted to changing conditions during the project lifetime, and hence it will operate as a live evolving document. After its initial submission in October 2022, the document has been updated in April 2024. This corresponds to the start of the second stage of the communication and dissemination strategy as first results start to become available. Another update is foreseen for project month 36.

2 OBJECTIVES OF THE DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The overall objective of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan is to ensure that information is shared with the most relevant external stakeholders in a timely way using the most effective communication channels. This document focuses on maximising the creation of impact both during and after the project duration and details outreach actions for deliverables, promotional material, and other project outputs.

Communication activities aim at providing general information about the project concept and objectives to all interested stakeholders in order to explain why the European Union invests into the CRM-geothermal project. More specifically, the communication actions will also inform the general public about the advantages of combined heat and metal

extraction with a view to reducing anxieties and increasing trust. This relates to the call aim of improving *“the awareness of the general public of the importance of need for a secure, sustainable and responsibly-sourced supply of raw materials.”*

The dissemination actions aim at transferring project results and knowledge to the most relevant stakeholder groups. They also intend to engage with stakeholders in a dialogue about the expected project outcomes with a view to supporting the future exploitation.

Finally, the exploitation plan aims at fostering the uptake of project results by the raw materials and geothermal communities. It will develop a strategy for incentivising the uptake of the proposed technologies and concepts by creating a roadmap for market development which will shorten the time-to-market for CRM-geothermal.

For internal purposes, this document also offers valuable guidelines to align messages and track dissemination activities and results.

2.1 TARGET AUDIENCES AND STAKEHOLDER MATRIX

The following chapter provides a mapping of the project’s primary target audiences. The proposed stakeholder matrix and engagement approach have been further refined in connection with the Milestone 10 report (Stakeholder Board established).

The main target audience of CRM-geothermal are the end-users of those mineral raw materials that are indispensable to make Europe the first digitally-enabled, climate-neutral economy. The request for more sustainable and domestic sourcing of primary raw materials has to come from the end-users, leading to a need for innovative technologies that satisfy this request.

Therefore, the primary dissemination target is the raw materials sector, industry associations and investors that can promote the market uptake.

CRM-geothermal is also expected to have an impact on the geothermal industry (operators, consultants, investors) by increasing the profitability of their operations.

Figure 1 displays the main target groups (from bright to dark with increasing importance for a quick market uptake of the technologies) for the dissemination of the outputs of CRM-geothermal that should be able to exploit the project’s results or enable a market uptake of the proposed technologies.

Figure 1: Main stakeholder groups of CRM-geothermal.

The above stakeholders constitute the target audiences of CRM-geothermal. The needs of these audiences is being assessed more in detail as results become available, to develop tailored outreach actions. Liaison with stakeholders will remain active throughout the project.

The stakeholder matrix serves to define the main groups of stakeholders and their needs based on their power and interest in the CRM-geothermal technology.

Many previous EU funded projects have investigated the topic of stakeholder mapping, covering the field of mineral raw materials ([INTRAW](#), [MICA](#), [MIREU](#), [SUMEX](#)) and geothermal energy ([CHPM2030](#), [REFLECT](#)). The stakeholder analysis of CRM-geothermal built on these results.

“Stakeholders are individuals, groups, or organisations who may affect, be affected by, or perceive themselves to be affected by a decision, activity, or outcome of a project, program, or portfolio.” (Friendman, 2006, in Tyrologou et al. 2022 - SUMEX deliverable 6.5).

Stakeholders are often mapped according to their power and interest related to a project (Hovland, 2005 and Mendelow 1981). Therefore, the **power** is the ability to exert influence over the implementation of the activity (either supporting or hindering). The **interest** stands for the level of concern from the stakeholder about the success or failure of the activity.

According to the power versus influence matrix, there are four quadrants of stakeholders (Figure 2):

- High power, high interest: engage closely and influence actively, high effort, regular detailed communication and dialogue, taking their view into account
- High power, low interest: keep satisfied, moderate effort, periodical information, keeping their view into account
- Low power, high interest: keep informed, moderate effort, periodical information and feedback

- Low power, low interest: monitor, least effort, periodical re-evaluation,

Figure 2: Stakeholder power/interest matrix (Adapted from Hovland, 2005).

The CRM-geothermal stakeholders have been analysed according to their needs and interest in the CRM-geothermal technology (Figure 3). The size of the bubble in the chart corresponds to the expected effort in engagement and communication.

Figure 3: Initial stakeholder mapping.

Analysing the stakeholders’ needs and power formed the basis for establishing the CRM-geothermal Stakeholder Board (see Section 3.3 Exploitation). All partners contributed to the compilation of the stakeholder database and the engagement with contacts.

EFG and GFZ developed guidelines for engagement with the stakeholders and maintain a GDPR compliant joint list of stakeholders restricted for internal use to map the CRM-geothermal network. This database was set up with a view to reaching Milestone 20, Stakeholder Board established, which was due in April 2023 (project Month 12).

2.2 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The CRM-geothermal project will use both electronic and conventional communication channels to reach out to the above-mentioned target groups. The main channels are listed here below.

2.2.1 Electronic communication channels

Website:

The project website has been set up at <https://crm-geothermal.eu/>. It acts as a central hub for all outreach activities, providing up-to-date information about the project’s aim and current status.

Social media channels:

The following social media channels have been set up:

- X (former Twitter): <https://twitter.com/CrmGeothermal>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86697981/>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/crmgeothermal/>
- TikTok: <https://www.tiktok.com/@crmgeothermal>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@CRM-geothermal>

A strong focus is put on LinkedIn, the major network for professionals, and X (former Twitter) which especially targets policy makers and the media. Instagram and TikTok are used to address the general public. A YouTube channel distributes all audio-visual contents.

The social media communication strategy that details actions, target groups and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: CRM-geothermal social media strategy.

	X (former Twitter)	LinkedIn	Instagram	TikTok	YouTube
Objectives /approach	Share project news, best	Share in depth-information	Share project news, best practices and	Share project news, best practices and	Release CRM-geothermal audio-visual

	practices and success stories on CRMs, geothermal energy, posting factsheets and infographics	about the project approach and results	success stories on CRMs, geothermal energy	success stories on CRMs, geothermal energy	material on a regular basis
Contents	Sharing factsheets, deliverables and infographics ; Two new tweets per week; Re-tweets of relevant content; Use of relevant hashtags; Tagging relevant institutions, projects, individual stakeholders and influencers; Translation by EFG AEs to increase outreach at national level.	Sharing factsheets, deliverables and infographics; Uploading presentations; Use of relevant hashtags; Tagging relevant institutions, projects, individual stakeholders and influencers.	Sharing pictures and audio-visual content; Organising photo contests; Creating stories; Use of relevant hashtags; Tagging relevant influencers.	Sharing audio-visual content; Organising contests and polls Opening discussions and creating two-way conversations; Tagging relevant influencers.	Short animations and gifs; Interviews with project partners, stakeholders; Event live-streaming.
Language	both technical and non-technical	technical	non-technical	non-technical	both technical and non-technical
Target groups	professionals, policy makers, media,	professionals, students	general public, especially young adults	general public, especially teenagers and young adults	professionals, policy makers, media, general public

	general public				
KPI	500 followers by the end of the project	500 active followers by the end of the project.	300 active followers by the end of the project	200 active followers by the end of the project	150 active subscribers by the end of the project

A preliminary list of **hashtags** to be regularly used on all channels has been defined:

- #CRMgeothermal
- #CRM
- #futureofmining
- #geothermal
- #lovegeothermal
- #geothermaldecade
- #sustainableenergy
- #zerocarbon
- #decarbonisation
- #renewables
- #renewableenergy
- #EU
- #HorizonEurope

Newsletter:

A bi-annual newsletter will inform stakeholders about the project progress.

Press releases and media kits:

Press releases will be issued on a periodic basis to keep stakeholders and media outlets informed on project outcomes.

Surveys:

Tailored online surveys will be used to gather relevant information from targeted stakeholders and to trigger dialogue.

Promotional material:

A focus will be put on electronic material to reduce the carbon footprint of CRM-geothermal activities. In this regard, a series of factsheets and infographics will be developed as well as two brochures. Only a limited number of hard copies will be printed for distribution at selected high-profile events.

2.2.2 Other communication channels

Consortium network

The consortium will make use of its existing communication channels and platforms to distribute information about CRM-geothermal.

For instance, EFG has two newsletters and a peer-reviewed open access journal, the European Geologist, that reaches 45,000 readers. In addition, the national re-publication of these articles by EFG National Associations which participate as Affiliated Entities in CRM-geothermal will be important vehicles to drive dissemination activities.

Table 2 provides an overview of some of the direct communication channels that will be used.

Table 2: Electronic and printed dissemination channels by EFG and its members.

Electronic dissemination channels by EFG and its members	
EFG	Monthly newsletter, 45.000 readers, GeoNews. Weekly news compilation, 45.000 readers, EFGGeoWeek
Belgium-Luxembourg	Monthly newsletter, 800 readers, Miscellanea.
Finland	Monthly newsletter with around 5.000 readers.
France	Weekly newsletter, 1.600 readers.
Germany	Monthly newsletter, 15.000 readers.
Hungary	Monthly newsletter, 1.300 readers.
Ireland	Biannual Newsletter, 400 readers.
Netherlands	Quarterly newsletter, 1.000 readers, Geo.brief.
Portugal	Monthly newsletter, 5000 readers, APGNews. Yearly electronic magazine with 18.000 readers.
Russia	Monthly newsletter.
Serbia	Newsletter, Vesti SGD, 300 readers.
Spain	Weekly newsletter, 3.000 readers.
Sweden	10 newsletters per year, 32.000 readers.
UK	Fortnightly newsletter, 10.000 readers.

Printed dissemination channels by EFG and its members	
EFG	European Geologist Journal, published twice per year, 45.000 readers.
Finland	Quarterly printed magazine, 5.000 readers.
France	Magazine Géologues, published quarterly, 1.200 readers Bulletin de la SGF, published bi-monthly, 1.200 readers. Géochronique, published quarterly, 1.000 readers.
Germany	Magazine BDG-Mitteilungen, published two times a year, 2.500 readers. Magazine Geowissenschaftliche Mitteilungen GMit (made in cooperation with 7 scientific societies), published quarterly, 9.500 readers.
Hungary	Földtani Közlöny, a scientific paper published quarterly, 1.200 readers.
Italy	Quarterly magazine, 15.000 readers.
Netherlands	Quarterly Scientific journal "Netherlands Journal for Geosciences".
Portugal	Magazine Geonovas, published yearly, 1.000 readers.
Spain	Magazine Tierra y Tecnología, published twice per year, 4.000 readers
UK	Monthly magazine, Geoscientist, 6.000 readers.

Other networks

The CRM-geothermal consortium members are firmly integrated into the professional and industrial raw materials and geothermal networks, thus ensuring a direct exchange of knowledge with important target groups. INTRAW has links to the UN Expert Group on Resource Management and is also partner in the SCRREEN2 project, thus having access to the European Expert Network on Critical Raw Materials, and a member of the European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA), actively contributing to its working groups. The findings of ERMA will inform the Commission's (DG GROW) raw materials policy making.

Several partners have strong links to the geothermal community (IGA-International Geothermal Association, EGEC- European Geothermal Council), ensuring that project results are fed to these stakeholder groups, resulting in uptake and follow-up activities.

CRM-geothermal consortium includes three geothermal operators (GEL, NI and CL) who already confirmed their interest in the proposed technologies. Cornish Lithium, as the third operator has even primary interest in CRM extraction, with an existing business plan for Li extraction from waters at their site in Cornwall. The participation of these operators guarantees a development of solutions adapted to operator's needs and, in return, a direct uptake of the investigated technologies.

Feedback to policy-making:

Several CRM-geothermal partners (GFZ, VITO, IZTECH, UKRI/BGS) are part of the EERA (European Energy Research Alliance) Joint program Geothermal. Project outcomes will be fed back to the EERA network, which influences the development of the EU's Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan). This channel guarantees an impact on European policy measures on the geothermal side. The INTRAW participation in SCRREEN2 and ERMA ensures a direct link to the EU CRM policy-making organs (DG GROW).

Clustering

CRM-geothermal also aims at clustering with other projects and initiatives. The main objective is to maximise the benefits of cooperating with other projects funded under the same Call in HORIZON-CL-4 (and projects funded by future CL-4 Calls in Horizon Europe) as well as projects funded by other EC programmes (e.g. Interreg, Life +), national research funds, public and private initiatives. The cluster of projects will cover geothermal energy and raw materials in addition to projects with complementary topics in materials science, socio-economics and the Green Deal. On the social media channels, links with other projects are established and dedicated clustering actions are developed under Task 6.6. The Clustering Network Map is displayed in Deliverable 6.7.

Conferences

CRM-geothermal will also utilise well established public relations tools such as conferences to reach policy makers, regulators, R&D funding organisations and other raw materials and geothermal stakeholders. Instead of organising such events explicitly for the project, CRM-geothermal aims to take advantage of the opportunities offered by other organisers and submit papers to existing specialised conferences, such as the European Raw Materials Week, Mines & Money, MINEX Europe, World Geothermal Congress and Exhibition, Annual Geopower Global Congress, IUGS International Geological Congress,

World Geothermal Congress, UCTEA Geothermal Congress and Exhibition, European Geosciences Union (EGU), Iceland Geothermal Conference and similar events.

The attendance of these events will be centrally coordinated and monitored by the WP6 leader to achieve the highest impact in terms of dissemination. In order to reach a broad number of stakeholders, conference attendance will be balanced between policymaking and policy implementation, research and technology development, finances and geosciences audiences. It is expected that CRM-geothermal will be presented at least 20 conferences worldwide. Networking opportunities complement this at a number of events that partners will be attending in a non-CRM-geothermal capacity.

Scientific publications

At least 10 peer-reviewed open-access publications will be made to publish the research outputs of CRM-geothermal.

CRM-geothermal will follow the open access publishing model, meaning that the scientific publisher will provide the scientific articles in open access mode. Accordingly, the associated costs will be shifted away from readers and will be covered by the project itself. Several partners have made explicit provisions for this, others will cover associated costs as overhead.

2.3 STAGES

The dissemination and outreach of CRM-geothermal encompasses three stages:

First stage:

The first stage aims to map relevant stakeholders and set up a network for CRM-geothermal, making intensive use of social media. This will create the basis for an active community of stakeholders engaged in relevant topics that will discuss, comment and consult on research and policy topics through the aforementioned channels. The WP6 leader (EFG) will ensure that key messages are delivered effectively to target audiences, matching communication and outreach objectives with the backgrounds and perspectives of the various stakeholders. This guarantee stakeholders' focus on core messages and leverage their interest around CRM-geothermal objectives and expected results. The existing networks of CRM-geothermal project partners and EFG affiliated entities (covering industry, academia, research, trade, NGOs, funding and governmental organisations) will play a pivotal role in multiplying the communication channels activated at this stage and will contribute significantly to reaching an active audience with multiple and diverse connections to relevant stakeholders for CRM-geothermal.

Second stage:

It will start by the end of Month 24, once the first results will become available. The set of public relations actions and tools will be widened to convey project achievements and their future extent to all identified audiences. The scope of dissemination will further focus on recruiting more stakeholders to the CRM-geothermal network, and it is expected that a broad network of stakeholders will follow the CRM-geothermal channels actively, allowing the project to foster engagement. This second stage will also benefit from reviewing the dissemination and communication plan scheduled for M24.

Third stage:

This stage will start at Month 36, after the second review of this document. Outreach activities will focus on conveying the research outputs of CRM-geothermal. At this stage, dissemination activities will be building on stage 1 and 2 efforts to increase the awareness of the target audiences and raise their expectations on the value of the developed technology solutions for Europe. Dissemination and outreach goals and activities will be reviewed at the start of this stage to ensure the best possible bond to the aims and principles of CRM-geothermal. Complementary to the above-mentioned approach, public relations tools, such as webinars and other events, will be used to reach the target audiences.

3 MEASURES

3.1 COMMUNICATION

CRM-geothermal communication activities aim to provide general information on the project concept and objectives to all interested stakeholders. More specifically, the communication actions will also inform the general public about the advantages of the proposed technology solution to develop trust in this approach that ensures an environmental-friendly and ethical supply of CRMs.

The following dedicated communication measures were planned since the beginning:

- At least two electronic factsheets will be designed to explain the benefits of the EU investment in CRM geothermal projects at the local and European levels.
- A series of at least five short videos will introduce the project concept and activities. A film-making workshop will allow researchers to record short videos about their research.
- An animation video will explain the project results. EFG's Affiliated Entities will ensure the translation of subtitles to increase outreach.
- A video contest for secondary school students will address the use of geothermal energy, the importance of CRM for our every-day life and the different faces of mining in Europe. EFG's Affiliated Entities will facilitate the contact with teachers.
- A media kit for journalists and policy makers will convey the key messages.

As of April 2024, the following actions have been implemented:

- During the General Assembly in Cornwall, the EFG team recorded a series of short [interviews](#) with partners to introduce the faces behind the project. In total, 13 interviews were recorded. The clips are published as part of a social media campaign that started in autumn 2023 with the aim of increasing interaction with non-technical audiences, focusing on Instagram and TikTok.
- In October 2023, EFG launched a [video contest for secondary school students](#). Students can participate individually or as a team with their classmates and are invited to submit a video addressing the following subjects: The key role of geothermal in fighting climate change; the importance of critical raw materials in your everyday life and/or; the importance of mining in their area. The deadline for submissions is 24 June 2024. EFG's Affiliated Entities actively promote the video contest in schools at a national level.

- To allow the CRM-geothermal research team to record impactful short videos about their research, EFG organised a film making workshop. The first part was held virtually on 20 April 2023. It covered the following topics: Storytelling I: What do I tell?; Storytelling II: How do I tell it?; Filming: How do I record and edit it?. Following this first session, participants were invited to prepare video concepts and/or first clips for a follow up session held during the second General Assembly in Cornwall (June 2023). As of October 2023, the project partners have produced 3 short clips (CL, IZTECH and VITO). In addition, INLECOM has prepared 3 draft video concepts for production later in the project.
- A media kit has been developed and actively distributed. It is available through the project website at <https://crm-geothermal.eu/media-information/>.

Communication directed towards the stakeholders at the pilot site of CRM-geothermal is coordinated with Task 4.2.

3.2 DISSEMINATION

The dissemination actions aim to transfer the generated knowledge and project results to the most relevant stakeholder groups. They also intend to engage with stakeholders in a dialogue about the expected project outcomes to support the future exploitation and uptake by industry.

The following dedicated dissemination measures were planned since the beginning:

- Once the first research results are available, at least five webinars will be organised for the stakeholder groups identified under Task 6.1.
- Approximately ten peer-reviewed open access papers will be published to reach out to the scientific community. Project results will be presented in at least 20 international events addressing the geothermal (e.g., International Geothermal Congress, EU Sustainable Energy Week) and the mining sector (e.g. EU Raw Materials Week). Results and datasets will also be published through the Horizon Results Platform.
- A series of at least five factsheets and infographics will inform operators and mining professionals about the industrial application, deployment, economic potential and societal benefits with a view to incentivising uptake. This will be complemented by a bootcamp at one of the pilot sites (event on-site and streamed online).
- Guidelines for operators and investors on extracting CRM in different geothermal (and societal) settings will be prepared.
- A summarising booklet for investors will explain the main results and benefits of using the project's approach.
- A high-level final conference in Brussels will communicate project outcomes and their impact on EU policy makers, public authorities, and other interested stakeholders.

As of April 2024, the following actions have been implemented:

- Project partners disseminated CRM-geothermal results in 13 conference presentations.
- A scientific publication was made on “Geothermal Energy and Its Potential for Critical Metal Extraction — A Review” (<https://doi.org/10.3390/en16207168>).
- A first webinar has been organised on 12 March 2023 in collaboration with the RAWMINA project. The recordings were made available online: <https://www.youtube.com/@CRM-geothermal>

The key outputs of CRM-geothermal will be public and made available to everyone. All data, including deliverables, will be made publicly available via the project website and the Zenodo repository (see D7.6), rendering them findable accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR). However, tailored dissemination efforts will target specific stakeholder groups, facilitating contact with the deliverables that might have more relevance to some groups. Table 3 outlines this approach and will be adjusted during the project's lifetime.

Table 3: Summary of project outputs to be conveyed through dissemination activities to target audiences.

	General public and consumer organisations	Public agencies and authorities	SMEs, other industries, technology platforms	Raw materials sector	Geothermal operators
<i>D1.1 Report on data obtained from literature review and existing databases included in the CRM-geothermal database (M14)</i>				x	x
<i>D1.2 CRM-geothermal database (data publication) (M38)</i>				x	x
<i>D1.3 Online GIS based CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas for Europe and Eastern Africa (M42)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D1.4 Final Version of AI-based simulation module (software prototype) (M36)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D2.1 Report identifying pre-existing sources of data at the selected sites (M8)</i>				x	x
<i>D2.2 Report on mineral characterisation of scales and CRM enrichment (high-enthalpy and alkaline fluid sites) (M38)</i>				x	x

<i>D2.3 Report on resource magnitude and sustainability of CRM in 5 geothermal settings (M38)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D2.4 Report on host rock characterisation and experimental leaching (M30)</i>				x	x
<i>D2.5 Report on resource calculation according to the UNFC (M40)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D3.1 Report on adsorption of Li and Sr by ion sieves (M40)</i>			x	x	x
<i>D3.2 Report on the development of ion exchange membranes and extraction fluids to selectively separate Li, Rb or Sr from geothermal brines (M36)</i>			x	x	x
<i>D3.3 Report on modified polymers as adsorbents and their effectiveness under geothermal conditions (M38)</i>			x	x	x
<i>D3.4 Report: Proof-of-concept oxalogenesisoxalatrophy pathway for biorecovery of Li and metals (M30)</i>			x	x	x
<i>D3.5 Report: Effectiveness of microbial biorecovery of metals from geothermal brines (M36)</i>			x	x	x
<i>D3.6 Report on membrane-based gas extraction from brine (M37)</i>			x	x	x
<i>D3.7 Report on the performance and applicability of the GDEx technology for the selective recovery of metals from geothermal fluids (M40)</i>			x	x	x

<i>D4.1 ESG due diligence of the combined extraction of CRMs and energy, incl. UNFC/UNRMS compatible reporting (M40)</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>D4.2 Guidelines for obtaining the Social Licenses to Operate (SLO) for combined extraction of CRM and energy (M36)</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>D4.3 Market analysis and decision support of the combined extraction of CRM and energy (M46)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D4.4 Innovative business models, sustainable revenue streams and roadmap for market deployment of combined extraction of CRM and energy M46)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D5.2 Tracer tests at the pilot site and hydraulic Model (M44)</i>				x	x
<i>D5.3 Numerical adsorption model for CRM extraction and sensitivity studies (M36)</i>		x		x	x
<i>D5.4 Report on miniplant process engineering, design and testing (M44)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D5.5 Report on the social studies at the pilot site (M45)</i>		x	x	x	x
<i>D5.6 Report on costs and economic benefit of all aspects of combined extraction at the site (M46)</i>	x	x	x	x	x

Table 4 below summarises the dissemination activities of CRM-geothermal based on a monthly delivery schedule. The scheduling of the activities is closely aligned with key project milestones (marked in **grey**). The majority of the activities (such as social networking or personal communication) are expected to intensify before and after key

project outputs (**orange** and **red** cells). These timeframes should be regarded as indicative.

3.3 EXPLOITATION

Exploitation actions focus on making concrete use of project results for commercial, societal and/or political purposes. Specifically in CRM-geothermal, the exploitation plan aims to foster the uptake of project results by the raw materials and geothermal communities, targeting researchers, industry, and policymakers. It will develop a strategy for incentivising the uptake of the proposed technologies and concepts by creating a roadmap for market development that will shorten the time-to-market for CRM-geothermal.

The following measures have been identified:

- The exploitation strategy will address:
 - 1) common and individual use of project results for further (research and commercial) actions,
 - 2) marketing the technology,
 - 3) commercial protection, and
 - 4) licensing.
- A complimentary Educational Plan will present:
 - 1) recommendations for university curricula in relation to geothermal and minerals resources, and
 - 2) guidelines for discussing the energy transition challenges for secondary school teachers, based on the video contest.

The Affiliated Entities of EFG will support the dissemination of the Educational Plan at a national level.

- A Stakeholder Board will be formed with interested professional stakeholders such as companies with experience from leaching in mines, geothermal operators (EU and Africa), companies from flooded coal mines, mine water associations or experts on volcanic systems. The Stakeholder Board will act as a multiplier towards target groups and thus ensure market uptake of project results.
- The project website will remain available for at least two years after the end of the project.
- All deliverables, scientific publications and data publications will be permanently archived by GFZ library and GFZ data services or comparable archives of other projects partners. In this way, the long-term availability of the project results will be assured.
- To support the exploitation of CRM-geothermal results, the project will also make use of available European Commission-related tools such as the Horizon Results Booster, the Horizon Results Platform and the IP Scan Service.

The exploitation strategy will be designed in collaboration with the business models and roadmap to be developed in Task 4.4, but also based on feedback collected from stakeholders and experts. The aim is to support the strategic exploitation of results individually and as a consortium in both commercial and non-commercial (academic, research, policy) domains. The planning of the exploitation measures has started from the beginning but will take more importance towards the end of the project (even beyond the funding period) and as soon as CRM-geothermal produces exploitable results.

During the Cornwall General Assembly in June 2023, project partners were invited to contribute to developing the project's exploitation strategy by completing a questionnaire concerning results considered exploitable. The input received has been analysed and considered for the draft exploitation strategy (see Annex 2). This activity is closely coordinated with Task 4.4 (LPRC) which is developing business models and a roadmap for the CRM-geothermal technology.

A Stakeholder Board was established based on the preparatory work conducted under Task 6.1 (Milestone 20, M12). Following the guidelines provided by EFG, the project partners contributed by contacting stakeholders from their network and inviting them to become part of the Stakeholder Board. Members benefit from the following advantages: First-hand insights into the CRM-geothermal research; contributing to the development of the CRM-geothermal technology by providing insights and expectations to bridge it to the market through foresight exercises (i.e., Focus Groups and Scenarios); obtaining official acknowledgement of their support to the project implementation. As of April 2024, 16 contacts replied positively to the invitation. To initiate engagement with the Stakeholder Board, a first webinar was organised in February 2024 to provide an overview of the CRM-geothermal project and introduce WP1 and WP2. A follow-up webinar on WP3, WP4 and WP5 is planned for the second half of April 2024. The ultimate objective for the Stakeholder Board will be to act as a multiplier and ensure market uptake of project results.

Complementary to the aforementioned a short exploitation strategy is provided in Annex 2.

4 IMPACT

4.1 MONITORING

Each partner is required to support project dissemination actively. Consequently, a "CRM-geothermal dissemination reporting table" has been filed in the project's internal repository (Folder 'WP6 – Dissemination' > 'Outreach') where each partner is expected to indicate on a regular basis implemented dissemination activities, such as presentations at conferences and workshops, publications in scientific journals or media for the general public, exhibitions, broadcasts on TV/radio, etc. Instructions for reporting the dissemination activities are provided at the beginning of the table and reminders will be sent to Consortium partners on a six-month basis.

To monitor the efficiency and success of the communication activities, the web and social media statistics are recorded and analysed on a monthly basis. This regular performance check facilitate fine-tuning the dissemination and outreach strategy whenever deemed appropriate.

4.2 KPIs

The table below summarises selected key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to assess the impact of CRM-geothermal dissemination activities. It also outlines the support expected from each partner.

Dedicated KPIs for social media outreach have been identified under section 2.2.1.

Table 5: List of CRM-geothermal dissemination channels and key performance indicators (KPIs).

Dissemination channel	Metrics	KPIs	Role of Partners	Status 04/2024
Project website	Number of hits, page views, and average time spent, deliverable/document downloads, emails/request for information received.	An average of 10.000 visits and 500 document downloads per year would be a positive result, with at least 30% of the users spending more than 2 minutes exploring the site.	Wherever possible, include the website link in email footers, communications and presentations. Supplying WP6 leader with photos, footage, text and regular updates on project activities.	Ca. 11.300 visits in 2023 Ca. 250 downloads in year 1
Social media CRM-geothermal LinkedIn CRM-geothermal X (former Twitter) CRM-geothermal Instagram CRM-geothermal TikTok CRM-geothermal You Tube	Flow of communication; number of members/followers, number of likes and shares, network page views, page comments, re-tweets.	By the end of the project, 500 active followers on X (former Twitter) and LinkedIn, 300 on Instagram, 200 on TikTok, and 150 on YouTube.	“Like”/“Follow”/“Subscribe” the CRM-geothermal accounts and regularly share/retweet its posts. Post at least twice per month project relevant news in your institution’s social media accounts.	X (former Twitter): 283 LinkedIn : 582 Instagram : 127 TikTok : 10 YouTube : 7
Newsletters CRM-geothermal newsletters GeoNews 3rd parties and Consortium members newsletters	Number of readers for the CRM-geothermal newsletters. Number of CRM-geothermal news in EFG’s GeoNews and Consortium members newsletters.	There will be dedicated CRM-geothermal newsletters every 6 months. The consortium aims at publishing project related news in at least 2 newsletters per year (per institution).	Include CRM-geothermal news at least once per semester in your institution’s newsletters.	1 newsletter published 14 newsletter entries
Marketing material Project brochures Factsheets Press releases/media kits	Number of brochures produced, translated, downloaded, printed and distributed.	Preparation and distribution of 2 different brochures (M6, M44) during the project’s life cycle; editing at least 5	Display the project brochure at all relevant events that you attend or organise. Factsheets and press releases should be	1 brochure, 1 flyer, 3 press releases + media kit

		factsheets and 1 press release every 6 months.	disseminated broadly within your institution's network and whenever possible translated to your own language.	
Publications Peer-reviewed scientific papers Journal publications	Number of scientific papers and abstracts submitted, number of journal articles published, type of journals (academic, industry), impact factor of journals.	The target in CRM-geothermal is to publish at least 10-15 peer-reviewed papers.	Identify appropriate publication opportunities and co-author at least one article with other consortium members.	1 paper
Events Webinars Bootcamp Final conference Clustering events	Number of events and attendance.	Organisation of at least 5 webinars and one hybrid bootcamp. It is expected that 100-150 people will participate at the final International Project Conference (M48).	Support the organisation and promotion of webinars, clustering events, bootcamp and final conference.	1 public webinar (also clustering event) 1 Stakeholder Board webinar
Project presentations at external events	Number of conference papers and presentations, type and size of events, number of attendees.	It is foreseen that CRM-geothermal will be presented at least 20 major international sectorial events; the average number of targeted attendees per event is estimated to at least 300-500.	Support the promotion of these events within your network.	25 presentations at events

A regular monitoring of the above KPIs not only allows to keep the project's communication and dissemination efforts on track, but also to stay alert concerning evolutions in the ever-changing communications landscape.

5 GUIDELINES FOR PARTNERS

The following chapter provides guidelines for partners to ensure a homogeneous visual appearance of CRM-geothermal and to align its key messages.

Any press release (or other publicly available document) shall be approved by the project coordinator and the WP6 leader, who will closely cooperate on this activity with the project partner(s) involved. Only once the project coordinator gives clearance the document may be made available to the general public.

5.1 KEY MESSAGES

While introducing CRM-geothermal to an audience, Consortium partners shall use the following key messages:

Key message 1

Geothermal fluids often carry high amounts of elements that the EU considers as 'critical' raw materials (CRM). Extracting CRMs from geothermal wells will help the EU attain the energy transition goals.

Key message 2

Combined extraction of heat and minerals from geothermal reservoirs has several benefits, it:

- *Minimises environmental impacts*
- *Avoids additional land-use*
- *Leaves no mining legacies*
- *Has a near-zero carbon footprint*
- *Contributes to the EU autonomy on the supply of CRM*

Key message 3

Although CRM are known to occur in geothermal fluids, there are still many uncertainties concerning their occurrence in different geological settings. The actual extraction process is also a major challenge requiring technology development.

Key message 4

The Horizon Europe-funded CRM-geothermal project addresses the energy transition challenges by advancing:

- *A comprehensive database of CRM in geothermal settings as decision-making basis*
- *Specific extraction technologies that allow to extract the CRM under given high temperatures and from complex brine compositions in a geothermal system during fluid production*

Key message 5

The CRM-geothermal project will develop untapped resources and solutions to help Europe fulfil the strategic objectives of the EU Green Deal and the Agenda for Sustainable Development, reducing dependency on imported CRMs.

5.2 VISUAL IDENTITY

The project logo must be placed on all published material (Figure 4). This includes not only promotional materials but also deliverables, event announcements, factsheets, infographics, presentations, and agendas. The logo is available in different file formats in the internal repository (Folder 'WP6 – Dissemination' > 'Visual identity')

Figure 4: CRM-geothermal logo.

These different logo versions are illustrated and described in detail in the project's stylebook, which forms Annex 1 of this deliverable. The stylebook furthermore provides detailed information on the project's colour palette, the fonts to be used and different templates made available to partners.

5.3 INFORMATION ON EU FUNDING

According to the Grant Agreement¹, the following rules apply while communicating about CRM-geothermal:

"17.2 Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

¹ See ARTICLE 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY, pp. 38-40.

Figure 5: EU emblems.

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

(...)

17.5 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 28).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5.”

5.4 PUBLICATIONS

According to the Consortium Agreement, prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other project partners at least 20 calendar days before the publication. CRM-geothermal partners have the right to object within 10 days.

According to the decisions during the first General Assembly, for conference contributions (posters and oral presentations), abstract submissions and press releases, prior notice shall be given to the project partners at least 7 days before the publication. CRM-geothermal partners can object within 4 days. Silence means approval.

Consequently, CRM-geothermal partners should upload their planned publications to the shared folder ('Publications') and notify the consortium. CRM-geothermal partners should voice only objections. Approval should not be expressed in order to avoid excessive email traffic.

In addition, all dissemination material (deliverables, papers, conference papers, presentations) should be checked for plagiarism before publication, using available tools. When re-producing material (figures, images, tables) from published sources, authors shall consider the applicable copyright rules.

5.5 PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

As of April 2024, the following promotional material is available for partners on the shared repository:

Brochures:

- Main brochure (October 2022)
- Business-card-size flyer (November 2023)

Media kit:

- Last version from April 2023

Presentation slides:

- Generic presentation (last version from March 2024)

Press releases:

- September 2022: [Launch of CRM-geothermal project](#)
- May 2023: [German Chancellor Olaf Scholz explores Kenya's geothermal potential with CRM-geothermal project partner](#)
- October 2023: [CRM-geothermal Project Successfully Completes Fluid Testing in Cornwall](#)

This list will be periodically updated with new versions of existing documents or new documents that will be made available to project partners.

To maximise the outreach at a national level, it will be preferable to translate the promotional material into as many consortium languages as possible. Upon demand, the

EFG team will either provide the design files of the English version or support the layout creation.

5.6 TEMPLATES

Different templates have been made available to Consortium partners via the project's internal repository (folder 'Templates'), and the project stylebook (see Annex 1) specifies the formatting rules for each of these.

Currently the following templates are available:

- Powerpoint template
- Deliverable template

5.7 GDPR

As of May 2018, the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) replaced the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. GDPR has been designed to harmonise data privacy laws across Europe and reshape how organisations worldwide approach data privacy. In CRM-geothermal, this concerns especially:

1. Web contact forms and email subscriptions where personal data is requested and submitted by the user;
2. Cookies and online tracking including on Social Media;
3. Event registrations;
4. Online surveys.

The collection of data will only be undertaken if explicit authorisation by data subjects is obtained by an informed consent procedure, which will be in place in all events/interviews/workshops with external participants. The request for consent will be given in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and understandable language, and will also detail the purpose of data collection and treatment.

5.8 E-MAIL COMMUNICATION

To increase efficiency, a standard email subject title shall be used. This will allow the project partners to quickly recognise CRM-geothermal related emails. These should include the project name [CRM-geothermal] and WP number (if applicable) in the subject title, followed by a more specific description of the subject and a deadline for feedback or reply (if applicable). You can see here some examples of subject lines:

[CRM-geothermal] KOM minutes draft – Comments deadline 2022/08/16

[CRM-geothermal] WP6 – Stylebook – Review deadline 2022/09/15

[CRM-geothermal] Happy Christmas!!!

To keep traffic down, if you have any query about an e-mail, please reply to the sender only. While sending emails, please also consider sending them only to people who are concerned by the subject matter.

For project internal communication, different mailing list have been established:

- All project partners: crm-geothermal@gfz-potsdam.de
- Legal contacts: crm-legal@gfz-potsdam.de
- Main contacts: crm-main-contacts@gfz-potsdam.de

For communication on the WP-level, it was decided not to set up mailing lists but to provide a contact list on the Nextcloud per work package. This way, people have a better overview of the persons included in the work package communication and can better check if someone is missing.

If new staff is joining the project, the partner's PI is requested to inform the coordinator about the new contact details and emails. The coordinator shall add the new staff to the mailing list and the work package contact lists where necessary.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The communication, dissemination and exploitation guidelines advanced in this document provide the CRM-geothermal consortium a clear pathway to effectively reach the project's outreach goals. The consortium will use this plan as a baseline that will be further reviewed, revised, and updated during implementation, while also considering the stakeholders' interests and needs and possible challenges that may arise during the project's lifetime.

This document shall be revised periodically, considering the regular monitoring of outreach and new information acquired. This will allow the communication strategy to be fine-tuned to serve the different stakeholder groups better.

7 REFERENCES

- Pavlos Tyrologou, Vitor Correia, Marko Komac, European Federation of Geologists, 2022: SUMEX DELIVERABLE D6.5, EU EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRY MAPPED KEY STAKEHOLDERS
- Hovland, I., Successful Communication. A Toolkit for Researchers and Civil Society Organisations. 2005, London, UK: Overseas Development Institute. 78.
- Mendelow, A.L., Environmental Scanning - The Impact of the Stakeholder Concept in ICIS 1981 Proceedings. 1981. p. 407- 417.

ANNEX 1: STYLEBOOK

CRM-GEOTHERMAL

STYLEBOOK

Summary:

This document defines the visual identity of the CRM-geothermal project and establishes a standard visual style to ensure consistency and maximise outreach.

Authors:

Anita Stein, Communication Manager, European Federation of Geologists

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the logo and the style guide of the CRM-geothermal project. The style guide defines the visual identity of the project and establishes a standard visual style to ensure consistency and maximise the outreach of the communication results. This document not only specifies the project's colour scheme and fonts, but also provides guidance to project partners on how to correctly use the logo and follow CRM-geothermal's visual identity.

This document is an annex of D6.1 which presents the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan of CRM-geothermal.

1 REFERENCE TO EU FUNDING

According to the Grant Agreement¹, the following rules apply while communicating about CRM-geothermal:

"17.2 Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Funded by the
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Co-funded by the
European Union

Funded by the
European Union

Co-funded by the
European Union

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

¹ See ARTICLE 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY, pp. 38-40.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

(...)

17.5 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 28).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5.”

2 PROJECT LOGO

2.1 GENERAL RULES

The logo must be placed on all published materials and documents/presentations illustrated for the public. This includes not only promotional material, but also event invitations, presentations or agendas. The logo is available in .jpg, .png and .svg format in the project’s internal repository (folder ‘Visual identity’ within the ‘WP6 Dissemination’ folder).

The right file can easily be found in the project’s internal repository with the same reference as indicated below.

File names:

- CRM-geothermal_colour.jpg
- CRM-geothermal_transp.png
- CRM-geothermal_vector.svg

The logo must be readable. Therefore, a minimum height of 10 mm must be maintained when it is reproduced.

Figure 1: CRM-geothermal logo.

2.2 HOW TO USE THE LOGO

2.2.1 Background

The logo shall be placed preferably on white or very light background. The logo shall not be placed on a background of any shades of blue and green. If the logo is placed on coloured background, there shall be sufficient contrast between the background and the logo colours. The logo can be used on darker photo backgrounds if the text is readable and the droplet visible. The photo shall not be overloaded.

Figure 2: The CRM-geothermal logo background.

2.2.2 Positioning

The logo shall be placed at a visible position:

- For publications: On the outside, preferably front, or if not on the back cover.
- For information made available by electronic means (e.g. website) and by audiovisual material (e.g. CDs, PPT presentations) this principle shall be applied by analogy.

Figure 3: The CRM-geothermal logo positioning in the presentation template.

2.2.3 Minimum distance

The logo needs a minimum space around to take effect. Therefore, a minimum distance 'A' has been defined, which all layouts must follow. This minimum distance shall not be reduced. The dimension of 'A' has been derived from the height of the droplet. The distance 'A' must be maintained above, below, left, and right of the logo.

Figure 4: The CRM-geothermal logo's minimum distances.

2.2.4 Proportions

If the logo is placed next to other logos, like the project partners' logos, it shall be at least as big as the other logos. The logo shall not be smaller than the other logos.

Figure 5: The CRM-geothermal logo proportions.

2.2.5 Don'ts

The logo shall not be modified with any different typography or colours than the originals. No artwork or typography shall be added to the logo. The logo shall not be placed on coloured background with insufficient contrast to the logo colours. The logo shall not be cropped or rotated. The logo shall not be placed on a background if this is overloaded with too many details.

Figure 6: Wrong use of the CRM-geothermal logo.

3 FONTS

The two font families are Fredoka One Regular and Open Sans. The font used in the logo is Fredoka One Regular and should also be used for headlines. As a general rule, Open Sans is used for subheads and body text.

Both fonts are available in the project's internal repository (folder 'Visual identity' within the 'WP6 Dissemination' folder).

Fredoka One Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Open Sans Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Open Sans Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Figure 7: The CRM-geothermal font families.

Open Sans is also the standard font for desktop publishing (Microsoft Word® or Microsoft PowerPoint® communications).

4 COLOUR PALETTE

CRM-geothermal has standards for reproducing colours so they will always look consistent, no matter where they appear. The CRM-geothermal logo should be reproduced in full colour whenever possible. The colours of the logo are the source for the standard colour palette and should be used throughout all communications.

For four-color process printing (also known as full-colour printing), please refer to the CMYK values shown. For desktop publishing, such as Microsoft®Word or Microsoft PowerPoint®, refer to RGB (print/on-screen). For Web applications, refer to the RGB values or Hexadecimal values. The CMYK values provided can be used on both coated and uncoated paper when printing. Although variations in colour will occur, try to match the colours as closely as possible.

PRIMARY COLOUR PALETTE

Used for text, colour fields, and accent.			
COLOUR DEFINITIONS	Green	Turquoise	Light Blue
CMYK	47C 1M 92Y 0K	88C 43M 62Y 29K	71C 2M 4Y 0K
HEXADECIMAL	#9FC13B	#237373	#20B7E2
RGB	159R 193G 59B	35R 115G 115B	32R 183G 226B

SECONDARY COLOUR PALETTE

Used for colour fields and accent colours, but not for text.			
COLOUR DEFINITIONS	Purple	Light Turquoise	Grey
CMYK	55C 100M 0Y 0K	34C 0M 12Y 0K	18C 13M 14Y 0K
HEXADECIMAL	#8b0a80	#b2e7e8	#D8D8D8
RGB	139R 10G 128B	178R 231G 232B	216R 216G 216B

Figure 8: The CRM-geothermal colour palette.

5 TEMPLATES

Different templates have been made available to all partners via the project’s internal repository (folder ‘Templates’ within the ‘WP6 Dissemination’ folder).

Currently, the following templates are available:

- PowerPoint template;
- Minutes template;
- Deliverable template;
- Poster template.

We specify here below a couple of formatting rules for each of these.

POWERPOINT TEMPLATE

Font: Open Sans

Headline colour: CRM-geothermal Green (see page 8)

Main text colour: Black (see page 8)

TEMPLATES FOR MINUTES, DELIVERABLES AND OTHER DOCUMENTS

Font: Open Sans

Font for captions: Open Sans

Font size for main text: 11

Font size for headlines: 14

Font size for sub headlines: 14

Font size for captions: 11

Paragraph distance: 1,0

Page margins: 2,5 cm

Headline colour: CRM-geothermal Green (see page 8)

Main text colour: Black

6 IMAGES

Images have impact – they should be chosen carefully.

- Focus on positive aspects of CRM-geothermal efforts;
- Use one strong image on the cover;
- Select images that are in focus, and that are colourful and bright;
- Photos that show people have in general a bigger impact;
- Always include photo credits and captions.

Any image from the project's field research activities should have clearance for publishing from the Project Partner(s) responsible for performing the operations. A selection of photos that can be used for deliverables and publications are available in the project's internal document repository (see the folder 'Images' within 'WP6 Dissemination and exploitation'). The copyright to be used is indicated in the name of the subfolders or the image files. In some cases, further details are also provided within the subfolder itself.

7 LINGUISTIC CONVENTIONS

The project's name "CRM-geothermal" shall always be written as indicated here, meaning 'CRM' in capital letters and 'geothermal' in lower case.

For all linguistic conventions we refer to the English Style Guide of the European Commission:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf

8 CONTACT

PROJECT COORDINATOR

German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ)

Contact: Katrin Kieling, Project manager (katrin.kieling@gfz-potsdam.de) and Simona Regenspurg, Scientific coordinator (regens@gfz-potsdam.de)

WORK PACKAGE LEADER DISSEMINATION

European Federation of Geologists (EFG)

Contact: Anita Stein, Communication Manager (anita.stein@eurogeologists.eu)

ANNEX 2: EXPLOITATION STRATEGY (DRAFT)

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D6.1 – ANNEX 2

EXPLOITATION STRATEGY FOR CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS AND GEOTHERMAL ENERGY

Author:

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Anita Stein, European Federation of Geologists, Communication Manager

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1 INTRODUCTION

CRM-geothermal presents a transformative pathway for introducing innovative concepts for commercial exploitation and digital transformation despite its relatively low target Technology Readiness Level (TRL). The project aims to demonstrate commercial and industrial viability, assess market opportunities and stakeholder needs, and encourage domestic CRM production while considering future technology-driven demand developments. It also addresses business development, policy recommendations, and knowledge dissemination to benefit relevant industries and SMEs, potentially leading to the patenting of technical solutions.

The exploitation plan will provide the basis for identifying obstacles and requirements and using foresight techniques to anticipate future market dynamics and technology-driven demand changes. Additionally, emphasis is placed on knowledge dissemination and patenting encourages further research and innovation, ensuring that the benefits extend beyond the project's boundaries and positively impact relevant industries and stakeholders. Ultimately, the exploitation plan offers a comprehensive framework for sustainable CRM production with wide-reaching economic, environmental, and strategic advantages.

1.1 BACKGROUND

The digital and energy transitions, the European Green Deal, and the Next Generation EU all rely on access to raw materials, crucial for Europe's climate-neutral and competitive industry. To ensure EU autonomy and sustainable supply chains, local sourcing within European nations is preferred over dependence on third countries, despite limited social acceptance and competition for land with agriculture and green technologies. CRM-geothermal proposes co-producing critical raw materials and heat from geothermal sources, reducing visible mining infrastructure and environmental impact. It aligns with European geothermal development and aims to improve the understanding of raw material content in geothermal systems. Co-utilisation of deep geothermal fluids for raw material extraction presents an untapped resource, and CRM-geothermal faces the challenge of developing practical extraction methods. With its small surface footprint, domestic raw material supply, reduced imports, and support for the energy transition, it emerges as a promising approach.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the exploitation plan are the following:

1. Common and individual uptake of project results for further research.
2. Higher Technical Readiness Level (TRL) commercialisation.
3. Technology transfer by the deployment of outputs in other sectors.
4. Marketing the technology to end-users with communication actions.
5. Patenting and/or licensing of technological outputs.

It is envisaged that the achievement of the objectives will facilitate:

1. Revealing new EU domestic CRM supply chains.
2. Trustworthy and ethical supply chains for CRMs.

3. Creating a new mining industry branch without the drawbacks and history of traditional mining.
4. Rise in geothermal projects driven by increased profitability in combined extraction.
5. New resilient business prospects for SMEs leading to well-compensated job creation.
6. Extraction technology applies to other sectors for innovative and environmentally friendly uses.
7. Results deployment for further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product, a process or creating and providing a service.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE REPORT

The report aims to provide the tools to implement a comprehensive exploitation strategy that will work in synergy with the business models and roadmap developed in Task 4.4 of the project. The aim is to support the strategic exploitation of results individually and as a consortium in both commercial and non-commercial (academic, research, policy) domains. The exploitation strategy will be developed to address:

- 1) Widespread and individual utilisation of project outcomes for subsequent research and business initiatives.
- 2) Promoting the technology.
- 3) Safeguarding commercially and licensing it.

A complimentary report section on the educational plan will present:

- 1) Recommendations for university curricula in relation to geothermal and minerals resources, and
- 2) Guidelines for discussing the energy transition challenges for secondary school teachers, based on the video contest.

The Affiliated Entities will support disseminating the educational plan at a national level.

The Stakeholder Board that has been formed will have access to the exploitation plan to act as a multiplier towards target groups and thus ensure market uptake of project results. In addition, the exploitation plan will be used to leverage the benefits of cooperation with other projects funded under the same Call in HORIZON-CL-4 (and projects funded by future CL-4 Calls in Horizon Europe) as well as projects funded by other EC programmes (e.g. Interreg, Life +), national research funds, public and private initiatives.

2 POTENTIAL TARGET MARKETS AND APPLICATIONS

The CRM-geothermal technology presents existing geothermal operators with a unique opportunity to enhance profitability and make a significant societal impact. By retrofitting or slightly modifying their processes and equipment, operators can extract critical raw materials (CRMs) from geothermal fluids, boosting their financial performance while aligning with environmental and ethical standards. This approach reduces dependency on imported CRMs, supports local economies, and contributes to the EU's green initiatives, such as the Green Deal and Sustainable Development Agenda. In essence, it enables geothermal operators to optimise profits and champion sustainable resource management simultaneously (Figure 1).

Installed geothermal energy capacity, 2022

Cumulative installed capacity of geothermal energy, measured in megawatts.

Data source: International Renewable Energy Agency (2023)

[OurWorldInData.org/renewable-energy](https://ourworldindata.org/renewable-energy) | CC BY

Figure 1: Data Page: Geothermal energy capacity, part of the following publication: Hannah Ritchie, Pablo Rosado and Max Roser (2023) - "Energy". Data adapted from International Renewable Energy Agency. Retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/installed-geothermal-capacity> [online resource].

2.1 SIZE OF THE MARKET REVENUE – TARGET USERS

Currently there are 339 operating geothermal plants, with further 24 more on construction stage, 86 at the pre-construction while further 62 plants have been announced. In addition some 10 plants have been retired (source: <https://globalenergymonitor.org/projects/global-geothermal-power-tracker/tracker-map/> accessed at 16/01/2024). From the above, is deduced that the current market size, plant wise amounts to 511 plants without taking into account the retired ones, which may still present a potential for critical raw material extraction.

Table 1 presents data on the number of geothermal plants from 37 countries. The table shows the number of plants in each country, regardless of their capacity, and separately lists those with a capacity exceeding 30 MW. The countries that possess units under 30 MW are given in bold font.

Table 1: Global Geothermal Plants by country. Additional geothermal units under 30 MW are also included for countries (<30 MW column).

Region	Country	Operating		Construction	Pre- Construction
		> 30 MW	30<0 MW		
Global Total		202	339	17	70
Africa	Ethiopia	0	0	2	3
Africa	Kenya	12	14	4	10
Africa	Tanzania	-	-	-	1
Africa	Uganda	-	-	-	2
Americas	Bolivia	-	-	-	2
Americas	Canada	-	-	-	0
Americas	Chile	1	3	-	2
Americas	Colombia	-	-	-	1
Americas	Costa Rica	4	6	-	2
Americas	Ecuador	-	-	-	1
Americas	El Salvador	4	5	-	-
Americas	Guadeloupe	-	2	-	-
Americas	Honduras	1	1	-	-
Americas	Mexico	8	20	-	-
Americas	Nicaragua	4	4	-	-
Americas	United States	41	113	1	6
Asia	Indonesia	32	46	9	18
Asia	Japan	9	10	-	-
Asia	Laos	-	-	-	2
Asia	Philippines	29	34	-	11
Asia	Türkiye	14	35	0	8
Europe	Iceland	20	20	-	1
Europe	Italy	8	8	-	-
Europe	Portugal	-	3	-	-
Europe	Russia	1	1	-	-
Oceania	New Zealand	13	13	1	0
Oceania	Papua New Guinea	1	1	-	-

source: <https://globalenergymonitor.org/projects/global-geothermal-power-tracker/summary-tables/>. Data is as recent as 2023.

2.2 GEOTHERMAL OPERATORS AND NETWORKS

Table 2 presents the current biggest operators in terms of geothermal capacity identified as key players.

Table 2: Geothermal Power Top 5 Operating Capacity by Owner (MW)

Owner	Operating Capacity (MW)	Operating Units Count
Calpine CORP	1,163	10
Energy Development CORP (EDC)	1,475	17
AboitizPower CORP	692	12
Kenya Electricity Generating Company (KenGen)	632	10
Comisión Federal de Electricidad (CFE)	620	8

source: <https://globalenergymonitor.org/projects/global-geothermal-power-tracker/summary-tables/>. Data is as recent as 2023.

The geothermal power operators listed in the Table 2 have a diverse source portfolio of energy production. Thus, the geothermal sector represents a part of their business. Their financial statements and particularly the indexes of 1) Net Income, 2) Total stockholder's equity 3) Cash, beginning of period and 4) Cash end of period \$ millions are not decoupled per energy sector and thus are not reported to avoid any bias and overestimation of the geothermal potential market size. However, for the report completeness the reader is referred to the following links that provide the Table 2 companies' financial statements:

- 1) Calpine CORP: [Calpine Reports Second Quarter 2020 Results](#).
- 2) Energy Development CORP (EDC): [EDC IR 2020 FS.pdf \(energy.com.ph\)](#).
- 3) AboitizPower CORP: [AP-SEC-FORM-17-A---2022-Annual-Report-\(04132023\).pdf](#)
- 4) Kenya Electricity Generating Company (KenGen): [kengen.co.ke/images/2023/KenGen-Integrated-Report23Final.pdf](#).
- 5) Comisión Federal de Electricidad (CFE): [COMISIÓN FEDERAL DE ELECTRICIDAD \(cfe.mx\)](#).

Additional operators are given below in Table 3.

Table 3 : Global geothermal operators.

Operator Name	Country	Key Characteristics	MW Capacity
Ormat Technologies	USA	Operates in multiple countries, significant in the USA.	1,200
Enel Green Power	Italy	Operates geothermal plants in Italy and globally.	769
Chevron Corporation	USA	Involved in geothermal energy in Indonesia and the Philippines.	Varies
Pertamina Geothermal Energy	Indonesia	Significant player in Indonesia's geothermal sector.	442
Mercury NZ Limited (formerly Mighty River Power)	New Zealand	Operates geothermal plants in New Zealand.	181
Reykjavik Energy	Iceland	Operates geothermal plants in Iceland.	210

Star Energy Geothermal	Indonesia	An important operator within Indonesia's geothermal industry.	647
Contact Energy Ltd	New Zealand	-	-

The geothermal market size is primarily shaped by its core, comprising technical operators. However, it extends beyond this core and encompasses peripheral stakeholders throughout the energy supply chain. This broader scope is evident in the data presented in the Table 4, which highlights the current global and continental geothermal associations. These associations consist of individual members and national associations, which represent multiple members.

Table 4: Geothermal association at national, continental and global scale.

Association	Location	Members
Geothermal Rising	United States	100
International Geothermal Association (IGA)	Global	5000
European Geothermal Energy Council (EGEC)	Europe	180
Australian Geothermal Energy Association (AGEA)	Australia	60
Global Geothermal Alliance	Global	52 country member and 53 organisation

2.3 GEOTHERMAL TOOL SUPPLIERS

Table 5 presents an indicative list of geothermal tool suppliers that may benefit from the CRM-geothermal and increase their revenue by offering coupled services to the geothermal sector.

Table 5: Geothermal tool suppliers.

Supplier Name	Description	Country
Baker Hughes	Offers geothermal drilling and wellbore construction services and equipment.	USA
Schlumberger	Provides geothermal solutions including drilling technologies and reservoir evaluation.	USA
Halliburton	Offers well construction, completion, and production enhancement services for geothermal projects.	USA
Weatherford	Specialises in drilling, well integrity, and reservoir solutions for geothermal applications.	USA
Boart Longyear	Provides drilling services and equipment for geothermal drilling applications.	USA
Gardner Denver	Manufactures drilling and compression equipment for geothermal exploration and production.	USA
Geothermal Development Company (GDC)	A Kenyan state-owned company that offers geothermal services and equipment, particularly in East Africa.	Kenya
MudPuppy	Offers drilling fluids and drilling equipment for geothermal and geotechnical applications.	USA
NOV (National Oilwell Varco)	Provides drilling and production equipment for various energy industries, including geothermal.	USA
Atlas Copco	Offers drilling rigs and equipment used in geothermal exploration and production.	Sweden

Geothermal Resource Group (GRG)	Provides consulting and technical services related to geothermal exploration and development.	USA
GeothermEx	Specialises in geothermal resource assessment and development services.	USA
Geothermics International Inc. (GII)	Offers geothermal exploration and development tools and services.	USA
Reynolds International	Provides geothermal consulting services, including reservoir modeling and exploration support.	USA
Geothermal Instruments Inc.	Offers tools and equipment for geothermal monitoring and data collection.	USA
Geoquip Water Solutions	Provides geothermal drilling and installation equipment, particularly for ground source heat pumps.	UK
Iceland Drilling Company	Specialises in drilling services for geothermal and geotechnical projects.	Iceland
Geotec Spa	Offers geothermal drilling equipment and services.	Italy
Gregg Drilling	Provides geotechnical and environmental drilling services, including for geothermal projects.	USA
KenGen (Kenya Electricity Generating Company)	Operates geothermal power plants and offers geothermal services.	Kenya
Entropy Geo	Offers geothermal exploration and reservoir assessment services.	USA
Renewable Energy Services (RES)	Provides drilling and geothermal loop installation services for ground source heat pumps.	UK
Geoteam	Offers geothermal drilling services and equipment.	Italy
Summit Drilling	Provides geotechnical drilling services for geothermal and environmental projects.	USA
Mawarid	Offers geothermal drilling services and equipment.	UAE
Geopower International	Specialises in geothermal drilling services and equipment.	New Zealand
Zorlu Energy Group	Operates geothermal power plants and offers geothermal services.	Turkey

2.4 STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS, VALUE AND VALUE CHAIN

A stakeholder analysis and value chain analysis were conducted separately as part of different actions of the project. The main findings are reported here to complement the current report. The analyses offered an insight of the coupled geothermal and critical raw materials sector's dynamics, key players, and the flow of value within the industry.

A stakeholder analysis identifies and assesses the individuals, organisations, and entities that have an interest in or are affected by the geothermal industry. A high level stakeholder analysis revealed the following:

1. The EU is a key stakeholder as it aims to achieve climate neutrality, promote sustainable industry, and secure access to critical raw materials (CRM). It plays a central role in policy development and regulation.
2. Local population in proximity of geothermal projects are also stakeholders. They may have concerns about the environmental and social impacts of geothermal and CRM extraction activities.
3. The geothermal industry stands to benefit from CRM-geothermal projects as they provide an opportunity to combine CRM extraction with renewable energy production, contributing to sustainability goals.
4. Traditional mining companies may have an interest in CRM extraction and could be affected by competition from CRM-geothermal projects.

5. Non-governmental organisations focused on environmental conservation and sustainability are stakeholders. They may advocate for responsible resource extraction practices.
6. Investors interested in ethical and sustainable projects may support CRM-geothermal initiatives that align with responsible value chains.
7. Energy companies involved in the transition to renewable energy sources have an interest in the success of CRM-geothermal projects.
8. Universities and research organisations can contribute scientific knowledge to understand the geological and geochemical aspects of CRM-geothermal systems.
9. End-users who either benefit to use locally sourced critical raw materials as well as the ones or from having access to geothermal energy through electricity or direct heating applications.

The main stakeholder target for the purposes of the project is the end-users of those mineral raw materials that are indispensable to make Europe the first digitally-enabled, climate-neutral economy (Figure 2). The request for more sustainable and domestic sourcing of primary raw materials has to come from the end-users, leading to a need for innovative technologies that satisfy this request.

Figure 2: Target groups (from bright to dark with increasing importance for a quick market uptake of the technologies) for the dissemination of CRM-geothermal output that should be able to exploit the project's results or encourage or enable a market uptake of the proposed technologies.

The primary target of the project for exploitation purposes is the geothermal industry (operators, consultants, investors) that can increase the profitability of their operations by coupling geothermal energy and critical raw materials extraction.

The stakeholder analysis has been conducted within the first year of the CRM-geothermal with focus on geothermal operators. The stakeholders identified form the stakeholders advisory body for the project with purpose to provide a client's feedback.

Below a value analysis in disaggregated format is provided to demonstrate the multifacet benefits of the CRM-geothermal technology. The value facets are as follows:

- Economic value by providing access to critical raw materials required for the digital and green transitions. This value includes job creation and revenue from CRM extraction and renewable energy production.

- Environmental value due to a lower environmental footprint compared to conventional mining. Contribution on reducing the environmental impact of resource extraction and promote sustainability.
- Social value by minimising visible large-scale mining installations. The CRM-geothermal technology can reduce social opposition and conflicts related to mining activities. It can also enhance local economies and infrastructure.
- Strategic value contributing to the strategic autonomy of the EU by reducing dependence on third countries for critical raw materials. It aligns with the European Green Deal's goals and supporting a transition to sustainable energy sources.
- Technological value by driving innovation in resource extraction, renewable energy integration, and sustainable practices, contributing to technological advancements.
- Ethical value by promoting ethical and responsible sourcing of critical raw materials, addressing concerns related to the ethical and environmental implications of mining.
- Policy value by aligning with EU policies on sustainability, climate action, and resource security, adding value by complying with regulatory frameworks.
- Scientific value by research conducted enhancing scientific understanding of geological, hydrological, and geochemical processes, contributing to the scientific community.

Understanding these stakeholders and values is essential for effective project planning, risk assessment, and stakeholder engagement in CRM-geothermal initiatives. It helps ensure that the project aligns with sustainability goals while addressing the concerns and interests of various stakeholders.

Understanding this value chain is essential for identifying opportunities for efficiency improvements, cost reduction, and value creation within the industry (Table 6).

Table 6: Elementary value chain analysis presentation for CRM-geothermal project.

Supply Side	CRM -Geothermal	User & Supply Side	Demand Side (end users)
Geothermal Operators	Coupling geothermal energy and CRM extraction	Mining Companies, Recycling and Refining Companies, Secondary Sources	Green technology, telecommunications, space exploration, aerial imaging, aviation, medical devices, micro-electronics, transportation, defence

3 ROADMAP FOR EXPLOITATION

The exploitation plan primarily consists in the engagement of secondary implementers (inside and outside regional networks), i.e. industry willing to adopt the concept/methodology after the project finishes. During the project, the secondary implementers will be supported in learning to use the tool and to collect necessary building stock data. Municipalities will use this knowledge to transform their building renovation policies and database frameworks. Trainings, which are not focused on the direct collaboration with the frontrunner municipalities will be conducted open to the public to attract, besides public stakeholders and decision-makers, market representatives as well as private investors.

3.1 EXPLOITABLE ASSETS

The Exploitation Plan is based on the following list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that form the tangible assets being developed in the CRM-geothermal project:

1. Adsorptive extraction by ion sieves and upscale the process for lithium.
2. Selective Ion exchange membrane technique for extraction of Li, Sr and Rb.
3. Selective reversible adsorption by means of modified (bio-)polymers.
4. Develop an ion enrichment technology by bioextraction.
5. Develop an extraction method for helium gas.
6. Enhancement of the method of gas diffusion electrocrystallization (GDEx).
7. Visualisation of CRM content in geothermal fluids from various geothermal formations across Europe and East African Rift countries through a fluid atlas
8. An AI tool designed to provide accurate estimations of Lithium concentrations while ensuring interpretability in geothermal data analysis.

The different types of exploitation are distinguished:

1. Commercially
2. Non commercially
3. Academic
4. Research
5. Policy

Table 7 provides the data from the collaborative effort between the partners that has resulted in the presentation of the aforementioned.

Table 7: Survey among project partners on exploitation of project outputs.

Partner	What are the exploitable results you plan to produce within CRM-geothermal?	Type	How can these result potentially be exploited? 1. Commercially 2. Non commercially a. Academic b. Research c. Policy
?	increase the efficiency of geothermal energy utilisation		commercially
?	Mineral & element content of rocks related to geothermal fluids		commercially & non-commercially (academic/research)
?	Helium content Data in various settings, extrabeton methods established		Research & Academia
BGS	Monitor and administrate UK minerals		Research
BGS	independent, non-biased 3rd party verification		no idea
BRILL	Identification of microbial species capable of extraction of lithium from the liquid phase. Understanding of the binding capacity and rate for lithium uptake.	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory	
Cornish Lithium	Data on fractured reservoirs in new setting/Cornwall - publish paper on fractured reservoir test work		Using data gained from test work and imorve understanding of geothermal reservoir - implement new DLE technologies
Cornish Lithium	Pump/airlift test results - flow rates, Li (geochemistry), connectivity studies		used to help model reservoir commercially useful to help hydrogeological degrees?

Cornish Lithium	Hydro-geochemical data from the CLL site & a geochemical model to forecast the lifetime of the pilot site		Commercially & research
Cornish Lithium	Understand the availability and exploitability of CRMs within geothermal fluids in Cornwall. Get a stronger hold on the frameworks and legislation surrounding the exploitation of CRMs in geothermal fluids. Impact of DLE processing plants, economically, socially, and environmentally. Attending conferences and events to publicise findings and to gain new contacts with experts in the field.	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory BUS: Business model (new or improved) DSG: Design (new or improved) INFRA: New or improved infrastructure or facilities	
EFG	Educational plan: 1) guidelines for universities in relation to geothermal and minerals resources, and 2) guidelines for secondary school teachers, based on the video contest.	PO: Policy recommendation, guidance, advocacy	Non commercially (academic)
EFG	Organisation of high-level final conference in Brussels	EVNT: Event (conference, workshop, seminar)	Non commercially
GEL	WP2: input to fractured granite env to understand potential CRM availability WP5: Active engagement in local community around a CRM-extraction project - Report on feedback & lessons learnt		WP2: Commercial - understanding what CRMs could be commercially extracted in Cornwall - understanding of supply chain in Cornwall WP5: Advice on best practice community engagement surrounding CRM extraction projects
GFZ	Find a proper membrane material to extract Helium from geothermal fluid		Commercially
GFZ	efficient method for Li extraction from brine		commercially to be applied by geothermal operators
GFZ	Screening of geological settings/geothermal setting for CRM -- database		non-commercially (research)

GFZ	Numbers on CRM-occurrence and mobility in the North German basin		exploited commercially more geothermal plants in sedimentary basins scientific publications
HI	Training of young researchers in SME	STAFF: Qualified Personnel (qualified personnel exchanges)	
HI	Knowledge for evaluating project feasibility and giving guidance to clients.	SERV: Service (new or improved)	
INLECOM	An AI tool for estimation of lithium concentration and a tool for supporting predictive maintenance strategies for geothermal plants		Commercially & academic/research
INLECOM	Data Engineering on the Reflect database. This result will help correcting and enhancing the database. Using the enhanced database, we will provide with interrelation functions between selected elements' concentration. Using the enhanced Reflect database we will develop a sophisticated AI flexible system that characterises the Geothermal Systems. Finally, a novel model of predictive maintenance for scaling which will help increase the efficiency of the geothermal power plants.	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory SERV: Service (new or improved)	
INTRAW	A system to calculate the economic mineral and energy potential of a geothermal reservoir		policy-making
INTRAW	T4.1 Guidelines for ESG Assessment MFRA for extraction system		commercially: training courses on ESG assessment
INTRAW	Innovative business models, sustainable revenue streams and roadmap for market deployment of combined extraction of CRM and energy	BUS: Business model (new or improved)	

INTRAW	Methods for SLO in combined extraction	PO: Policy recommendation, guidance, advocacy	
INTRAW	Market analysis & decision support of the combined extraction of CRM + energy	METH: Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)	
LPRC	solid network of potential end-users of the results --> ClusterHub		Non-commercially or indirectly commercially --> network
LPRC	Co-organisation of the Cluster Workshop at Raw Materials Week 2023	EVNT: Event (conference, workshop, seminar)	
LPRC	A roadmap for market deployment	BUS: Business model (new or improved)	
LS	guidelines for SLO in multiple stakeholder settings		non-commercially (policy)
UKRI	Better understanding of fluid-rock processes in fractured granite.	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory	
UNES	a combination of learning and developing networks with companies	LEARN: Learning or Training (learning modules, curricula)	
UNIM	Broad, explanatory database supporting CRM-geothermal purposes		academic/research - commercial: supporting investment
UNIM	European Fluid Atlas & UNFC methodology development		Fluid atlas: non-commercially (research) UNFC: commercially
UNIM	database on geothermal wells, fluids, rocks		non commercially (academic, research, policy) - commercially (decision making based on the database)

UNIM	CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas as a visualisation, query and data access interface for the database.	PROD: Product (new or improved)	
UNIM (Istvan)	The database/atlas made available online		non-commercially: reserach/academic
Unine	microbially-produced Li and Sr carbonates from actual brines		commercially (continuous bioreactor) AND non-commercially (academic/research)
UNINE	Proof-of-concept that combining fungal oxalogenesis to bacterial oxalotrophy has the potential to immobilize soluble Li in geothermal brines as a solid and pure carbonate mineral, LiCO ₃ .	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory METH: Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)	
UNIPD	New ion-exchange materials, highly efficient and selective		commerical exploitation (possible) research (improve understanding ion-matter interaction)
UoI	CRM flux from geothermal fluids	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory	
VITO	GDEX allows direct Li-recovery from synthetic streams and real brines. The Li-enriched solid displays presence of layered double layer hydroxides	SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory DSG: Design (new or improved) METH: Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)	
VNI	Improving expertise on operating a geothermal power plant and combined Li-extraction plant	PROC: Industrial process (new or improved)	

3.2 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS AND FEATURES OF THE CRM-GEOTHERMAL TECHNOLOGY

The CRM-geothermal technology aims to advance the geological, hydrological, and geochemical understanding of these systems, particularly in terms of their CRM content. It explores the potential of deep geothermal fluids, which are rich in dissolved metals and gases of commercial interest, for co-utilisation in both energy production (heat and electricity) and the extraction of valuable elements. This dual-purpose approach not only enhances the economic viability of geothermal projects but also contributes to the creation of domestic CRM supplies, reducing dependency on imports (see also Grant Agreement, page 117). The technology exploits geothermal fluids across a spectrum of temperatures, with higher temperatures correlating to hydrothermal fluids capable of depositing metallic ore bodies. These fluids, often originating from hot, hydrous magmatic systems, are instrumental in the precipitation of metallic elements, thereby facilitating the extraction of valuable metals such as copper (Cu), lithium (Li), zinc (Zn), gold (Au), and silver (Ag) from active or dormant volcanic systems.

The technology is currently under investigation for its potential in various geothermal settings, including the extraction of lithium from metal-rich brines in projects such as the Cornish Lithium Ltd/Geothermal Engineering Ltd 'Geo3' project in Cornwall, the Salton Sea area in the USA, and Vulcan Energy Resources in the Upper Rhine Valley of Germany. Additionally, it explores the use of flooded mines with high mineralisation, such as abandoned coal mines in Western Germany, as low enthalpy geothermal resources.

One of the primary challenges addressed by CRM-geothermal technology is the development of practicable extraction methods for CRMs from geothermal fluid during the heat production process. The technology adopts a minimalistic approach to surface infrastructure, requiring little additional land use, with negligible CO₂ emissions, and ensuring no significant impact on the generation of renewable energy. Its technical specifications and features underscore the dual benefits of securing domestic CRM supplies and enhancing the economic viability of geothermal energy, marking a significant step forward in the energy transition.

3.3 STAND-ALONE TECHNOLOGIES

CRM-geothermal builds on technologies that can collectively move the state of the art and present the opportunity to benefit technical development in their own way. In addition to section 3.1 further expansion into these technologies is given below. Investigations into Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE) technologies, employs ion sieves made from manganese oxide, titanium oxide, or aluminium hydroxide, are underway to facilitate the extraction of lithium carbonate or hydroxide from brines to achieve "battery grade" purity. Despite these technologies' promise, information on their success in scaling up is sparse, and there is a clear need for further refinement and optimisation of these extraction processes.

Regarding the separation of strontium, research has been conducted on the use of crown ether type ligand systems as complexing agents for isolating caesium, strontium, and barium from radioactive waste. The structural rigidity of crown ether molecules enables high selectivity for elements with specific ion radii and the creation of stable coordinative bonds. However, significant adaptations are required to make these adsorption methods

viable in geothermal environments, which are characterised by extreme conditions of high temperature, pressure, and salinity.

In the domain of gallium and germanium recovery, the recycling industry has noted the development of chelating materials that include functional groups such as phosphonates, catechol, and hydroxy-oximes. The use of polymers from diverse compound classes as carrier materials, which are then derivatised, has been a strategy to simplify the management of these adsorption materials.

The project includes the deployment of an AI-based module/toolbox aimed at advancing geological understanding through the modeling and characterisation based on actual site data. This approach is intended to facilitate exploration efforts and provide insights into the geological history and structural models of areas under investigation. This technological integration signifies a step forward in developing and applying innovative mineral extraction and environmental management solutions.

3.4 FEATURES OF THE CRM-GEOTHERMAL ECOSYSTEM

CRM-geothermal builds on multidisciplinary to understand and leverage critical mineral resources within geothermal environments. Future partnerships with geothermal site operators will provide vital access and information, enriching the ecosystem's understanding of its surroundings and allowing for exploring and exploiting specific features such as metal-rich geothermal fluids or unique mineral compositions within geothermal reservoirs. The synergistic relationship between CRM extraction and geothermal energy production opens doors for integrated business models that capitalise on both sectors, fostering economic growth while advancing sustainable resource utilisation.

Aligned with principles of harmony and balance, CRM-geothermal seeks to minimise its environmental impact while maximising its positive contributions. This fosters mutual understanding and cooperation by promoting sustainable transparent resource management practices.

3.5 EXPLOITATION MODELS

Different business models can be used to exploit critical raw materials and geothermal energy. Two main models are briefly presented here, cooperative and Joint ventures.

Cooperative models involve stakeholders cooperating to exploit the resources, sharing the risks and benefits. In the CRM-geothermal context, a cooperative model could involve a company with mining experience working together with a university with expertise in geothermal energy.

Joint venture models include different stakeholders to form a joint venture to exploit the resources, sharing ownership and control. From the CRM-geothermal perspective it can involve a mining company and a geothermal company could form a joint venture to exploit resources in a particular area.

3.6 COMMERCIAL PROTECTION

The project is tuned to offer innovative, attractive, affordable solutions that present the potential for economic success. The intellectual property rights (IPR) equip the project with a competitive advantage in the market based on protection and information (Figure 3). It provides efficient and strategic knowledge management, including safeguarding and protecting intangible assets. The security will offer the protection to use, sell or licence any outputs. In contrast, the information will inform the stakeholders of the technical developments on the subject matter and stimulate further innovation to society's benefit. The project aims to merit value within the Europe Horizon value creation mechanism and provide valuable intellectual, intangible assets to support the competitive advantage of the EU in the increasingly contentious global arena. The ultimate goal is to support the EU to transform from a capital intensive economy to an innovative one. The IPR will form the intangible assets of the consortium intellectual outputs. In addition, development at the early stages of the project will avoid clashes and conflicts within the consortium.

Figure 3: IPR in the project process.

The CRM-geothermal strategy is to ensure property or assignment of the consortium IP rights without compromising the open data policy of Europe Horizon. Therefore, the following four categories will establish the IPR:

1) Patent or utility model ownership – The consortium will establish ownership registered for IPR rights and benefits. Each partner or jointly will apply to the European Patent Office to get invention protection. In addition, ownership will be preserved with the specific clauses in the consortium agreement which details on how the IP will be used and each partner's rights and obligations.

2) Trademarks ownership – The project will establish a logo for a trademark protected by registration if this is decided by the board. The consortium may investigate the availability of certain signs/symbols before registering any potential trademark to avoid conflict with registered goods and services that may operate under it. The Madrid Agreement will be deployed as an international system if the consortium uses a trademark abroad. The consortium may invest in identifying the registration of trademarks to exploit the procedures' additional advantages. The trademark will enable to track ownership and control licencing or franchising agreements.

3) Copyright between partners will be administered based on the already signed Consortium agreement. Attention will be given to moral rights. In the case of open data in the spirit of the Europe Horizon framework, the current Creative Commons copyright licences type of licence to protect intellectual property and expression of ideas will be deployed. The project will provide its data based on the Creative Commons copyright licences as they fit. These will be: CC BY, CC BY-SA, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC, CC BY-NC-SA, CC BY-NC-ND.

4) Undisclosed information (Trade secrets and data) Trade secrets will be protected against unauthorised use, including through breach of contract or confidence or other acts contrary to honest practices. Such protection is conditional upon the secret information, as it will have commercial value.

IP assessment

A dedicated team drawn within the consortium will be formed to perform IPR due diligence and assess and prioritise IP assets during the project’s life. As a first step, the team will conduct the due diligence on the following databases: a) [Wipo patentscope](#) b) [USA Patent and Trademark Office](#) c) [European Patent Office](#) and d) [Google patents search](#), e) [Wipo Global Brand Database](#), f) [European Union Intellectual Property Office](#) while support will be sought from the European IP Helpdesk. Next, the team will identify the future IP assets of the project and move forward to register them if that is possible and profitable (Table 8). After the registration, the team will also be responsible for monitoring the current market landscape for the emergence of new IPR that may impact the project’s business value. The latter will align with the IPR strategy and focus on a priority list. Thus if copywriting is more important, the team will base its efforts towards that direction. The priority list will enable the team resources to be used efficiently and identify the optimum business opportunities in the market landscape.

Table 8: Existing and New IPR

	Existing IPR	New IPR
Terminology	Knowledge exists before the project and is the property of each participant that contributes it.	Knowledge created during the project by the partners.
	Ownership does not change (what I owned before the collaboration I own after the collaboration)	Individual ownership (Partner owns the foreground they create) Joint ownership (Partners jointly share foreground created in the consortium)
	Access rights: Every participant can license and or offer user rights to another participant’s results or background, thus allowing beneficiaries to benefit from each other’s resources and taking full advantage of the collaboration	

The priority list will take into consideration the following aspects: **a)** strategic position, **b)** jurisdictional differences, **c)** strategic value and support, **d)** financial limits and support, **e)** financial limits or benefits, **f)** ownership, **g)** operational capability, **h)** operational impact and risk assessment.

The IPR team business, technology and strategic skills will be contemplated with legal ones. External specialised legal support will be sought if the organisation’s legal departments cannot fulfil this requirement. This will ensure that legal requirements to maintain the intangible assets are met and follow through the patent complex application process. The IPR team will meet quarterly during the project implementation and revise its strategy and priorities based on the evolving market landscape.

3.7 COMMERCIALISATION AND MONETISATION OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

The WP4 team will investigate the potential for commercialisation and monetisation of the IP assets and the financial resources required. This will consider core and non-core assets while providing the opportunity of licensing IP rights to secure future revenue to increase its business without increasing any associated risk.

3.8 NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENTS (NDA)

Confidentiality agreements, also known as non-disclosure agreements (NDAs), are legal instruments designed to protect sensitive information shared between parties during collaborations or transactions. If a confidentiality agreement becomes necessary, it is essential to clearly define the scope of confidential information, including proprietary technology, trade secrets, or other sensitive data, as well as specifying the obligations of the CRM-geothermal partners involved regarding the handling, use, and protection of this information.

Key elements to consider in drafting include outlining the agreement's purpose, defining the duration of confidentiality, establishing permitted uses and disclosures, and detailing procedures for securely handling and storing confidential information. Additionally, clauses addressing exceptions to confidentiality, dispute resolution mechanisms, and remedies for breaches should be included to ensure the enforceability and effectiveness of the agreement. Collaborating with legal experts familiar with relevant laws and regulations from European Union and the associated African countries is advisable to ensure that confidentiality agreements are tailored to the specific needs and circumstances of the parties involved, providing comprehensive protection for sensitive information while promoting trust and transparency in business relationships within the consortium.

3.9 MONITORING INNOVATIONS

The project partners can build on the current existing tasks described in the relevant WPs to identify the development of the CRM-geothermal technology landscape. The monitoring activities include:

1. Patent Searches: Regularly conducting patent searches can help identify if there are new filings related to your field of interest, including geothermal energy innovations.
2. Industry Publications: Subscribing to and reviewing industry-specific publications, journals, and newsletters can keep you informed about the latest research and developments.
3. Technology Scouting: Engaging in technology scouting through the WPs teams may lead to identify emerging technologies and innovations.
4. Networking: Participating in industry conferences, workshops, and seminars is a great way to stay connected with peers and learn about new technologies and innovations.

Further to adapting and getting updated in the relevant technology landscape, the aforementioned actions effectively serve to prevent counterfeiting and piracy of the technology. This includes monitoring the market for unauthorised use of the technology and taking legal action against infringers.

3.10 LICENSING

Creating a licensing plan for CRM-geothermal technologies involves several key steps to ensure that the intellectual property (IP) generated by the project is effectively commercialised, while also promoting its widespread adoption in a manner that respects the IP rights. While this task will be fully developed in Task 4.4 an abridging version is offered below to bridge the exploitation strategy and D4.4.

In the process of developing a coherent plan for licensing within the CRM-geothermal project, it begins with a meticulous IP Audit and Portfolio Management phase. This initial step involves conducting a comprehensive audit to identify and catalogue relevant innovations, technologies, and related intellectual property developed. This encompasses patents, trademarks, software, and any proprietary know-how integral to the project. Following this, an assessment of the commercial value for each IP asset needs to be undertaken, taking into account factors such as market demand, applicability across different geographies, and the potential each asset has for creating competitive advantages.

Subsequently, a Licensing Strategy with primary objectives for licensing out the technology will be defined. The goals will include maximising revenue, encouraging widespread adoption to facilitate innovation within the geothermal sector. An analysis of the target market similar to section 2 of this report will be performed to identify potential industries, sectors, or specific companies that could benefit from the CRM-geothermal technologies. This analysis will not only consider the needs and challenges faced by potential adopters but also evaluates the unique value proposition offered by the technology. Additionally, a review of the competitive landscape is essential to strategically position the CRM-geothermal IP, taking into account competing technologies and licensing models present in the market (§ 3.6).

The next phase involves selecting Licensing Models and Terms, where a decision is made regarding the most appropriate licensing models—be it exclusive, non-exclusive, or sole—based on the technology's market potential and the overarching objectives of the project. This phase requires the development of detailed terms and conditions that outline the use of the technology, sublicensing rights, royalties or fee structures, the duration of the license, geographic limitations, and any performance obligations. These terms are designed to ensure clarity and mutual benefit, including provisions for technology updates and improvements, thus laying a solid foundation for successful licensing agreements.

4 STAKEHOLDER BOARD

A Stakeholder Board has been formed with interested stakeholders, such as companies with experience from leaching in mines, geothermal operators (EU and Africa) and energy experts from the academia and industry. The Stakeholder Board acts as a multiplier and ensures the project's results are disseminated and implemented effectively. The exploitation strategy establishes how the Stakeholder Board will fulfill this role, which could include promoting the project's technology to their networks, sharing best practices and lessons learned, or advocating for the project's goals with policymakers or other relevant stakeholders.

The Stakeholder Board will provide input and guidance on the project's goals, plans, and strategies. This could involve reviewing project reports or plans, providing feedback on research findings, or offering guidance on how to engage with stakeholders. In addition, the members will serve as supporter for the project and its goals, promoting the project to their networks and advocating for its objectives with policymakers and other relevant stakeholders.

In the long term, the Stakeholder Board may evolve to facilitate market uptake of the project's results, including helping to identify potential users, facilitating access to project results, and promoting the technology to potential partners or customers. Finally it can serve as a liaison between the project team and relevant stakeholders, helping to connect the project with key players in the industry or academic community, and facilitating collaborations or partnerships.

5 CONCLUSION

The document details a strategic position that considers relevant institutions and networks for the uptake of CRM-geothermal, defines target customers and the corresponding value propositions, touchpoints to interact with prospective customers, examples of relevant customer relationships to implement, potential revenue streams, resources necessary to capture the value of CRM-geothermal assets, and key activities that should be implemented immediately and on the short- and medium-term.

The targeted market contributors that are paramount to successfully exploiting CRM-geothermal results are the industry and suppliers, with particular emphasis primarily on geothermal and secondarily on mining companies and tertiary providers of geothermal equipment and technology. Geothermal operators can access testing/demonstration sites, offer expertise within specific domains, contribute to system integration and present valuable market insights. Further to the aforementioned, the CRM-geothermal Consortium, comprising diverse research institutions, universities, SMEs and NGOs is an invaluable resource, granting access to cutting-edge knowledge, expertise, and facilities. These partners are pivotal in developing advanced algorithms, conducting specialised research, and providing valuable insights to successfully uptake CRM-geothermal.

The engagement with these key players should start immediately (i.e. before the end of the funding period), and focus on:

- Obtaining referrals (to be published on social media) from project partners, members of the CRM-geothermal Stakeholder Board and industry partners who hosted field trials to leverage positive word-of-mouth and attract potential industry partners/target customers;
- Initiate direct outreach activities targeting geothermal and mining companies seeking the development of partnerships for test trials and/or joint research and development;
- Identify public funding opportunities.
- Determining the optimal future steps, crucial for the uptake of CRM-geothermal assets, will hinge upon the outcomes of the immediate engagement efforts.

Future short- and medium-term actions will necessarily encompass the following actions:

- Designing and optimising a replicable CRM extraction process;
- Conducting rigorous testing and validation to ensure reliability, repeatability and reproducibility ;
- Collaborating with end-users or customers for real-world deployment;
- Integrating the system with existing infrastructure or processes;
- Establishing strategic partnerships and collaborations for market access;
- Continuously analysing and optimising the business model for revenue generation;
- Protecting and managing intellectual property rights.

It is also essential to emphasise that the CRM-geothermal Consortium retains ownership of the project's background and foreground intellectual property rights.